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Abstract

This report examines initiatives, standards, and platforms that support crediting, recognition, and rewards for researchers, with a focus on research software and training activities. It explores existing efforts to reform research assessment, highlighting mechanisms that promote career progression and collaboration. Key standards (e.g., CodeMeta, CFF, CRO) and platforms (e.g., ORCID, APICURON, BIP! Scholar, OpenEBench) are identified, demonstrating their role in structured attribution. Despite progress, challenges remain in tracking contributions, standardising recognition, and ensuring interoperability. Addressing these gaps is essential for fostering open science, scientific sustainability, and an equitable research ecosystem.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides an in-depth examination of current initiatives, standards, and platforms that can support the transition towards an inclusive crediting, recognising, and rewarding framework for researchers with an emphasis on research software and training activities. The analysis seeks to illuminate the mechanisms in place, identify gaps, and propose actionable recommendations to enhance the visibility, equity, and impact of these contributions within the research ecosystem.

The report first explores existing work for reforming research assessment, credit, recognition, and rewards for researchers across academic contexts. It examines their recommendations on supporting career progression, promoting collaboration, and advancing the development of research software and training activities. The scope encompasses literature reviews, key initiatives, established standards, and current platforms to provide a comprehensive understanding of the landscape.

Research software and training activities are pivotal to scientific innovation across disciplines. Despite their significance, contributions in these domains are frequently undervalued within traditional academic recognition systems. Understanding and improving mechanisms to recognize these efforts is vital for fostering motivation, advancing open science, and ensuring long-term scientific reproducibility and sustainability.

Our analysis identifies numerous initiatives for research assessment, credit, recognition, and rewards, including global declarations, such as DORA and CoARA, as well as numerous community-driven efforts. These initiatives, among others, emphasize transparency and inclusivity in acknowledging various types of research contributions including research software and training activities. Key standards, such as CodeMeta, CFF, and CRO, and platforms, such as ORCID, APICURON, BIP! Scholar, and OpenEBench, that can be used to provide structured mechanisms for attributing credit for research software and training activities were also identified and their potential role was explained. We offer a classification of those resources into broad categories of components that are required for the implementation of inclusive credit, recognition, and rewards mechanisms and we provide a conceptual architecture demonstrating how they can be combined for this purpose.

Despite the fact that a lot of required components already exist, significant limitations persist. More specifically, tracking specific types of research contributions, including software and training activities, faces limitations in the existing platforms and there is a need for extending the relevant functionalities to include tailored indicators, templates, and components. Apart from that, there is a need for enhanced standardization in the ways the respective activities are recognised as well as for improved interoperability across existing platforms. Addressing these challenges will be crucial in optimizing their effectiveness and ensuring seamless implementation.

In conclusion, optimizing the rewards and recognition landscape for research software and training activities is crucial for advancing scientific progress, fostering collaboration, and valuing the diverse contributions of researchers and RSEs. Addressing the identified gaps and leveraging emerging practices will help build an inclusive and equitable ecosystem that fully acknowledges all forms of scientific contributions.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, the work of researchers encompasses a wide range of activities that contribute to the creation and dissemination of scientific knowledge. Beyond traditional publications, researchers engage in dataset creation, software development, conducting training events, preparing educational material, and other activities which are integral to the research process. Consequently, robust and inclusive recognition and reward mechanisms for researchers, ensuring that all research-related activities and contributions are acknowledged and valued, are of utmost importance for supporting researchers in their career progression and fostering good practices in all aspects of research. Highlighting and rewarding diverse contributions encourages a holistic approach to research, incentivises researchers to strive for excellence, and fosters a culture of appreciation within the scientific community.

One of the objectives of the EVERSE project is to deliver a comprehensive framework for crediting, recognising and rewarding research activities related to research software engineering and training. To this end, the current report offers an extensive landscape analysis of the current practices for credit, recognition, and rewards in research as well as of the relevant initiatives and platforms available. This analysis will be used by EVERSE partners as a basis for envisioning a robust and inclusive framework for crediting, recognising, and rewarding research software engineering and training activities.

2 Background and challenges

Scientific research deepens our understanding of the world and leverages this knowledge to enhance our lives, enable technological innovations, and stimulate economic growth. Researchers dedicate significant effort in research-related activities making significant contributions towards these goals. Consequently, robust and inclusive mechanisms for crediting, recognizing, and rewarding these activities and contributions are crucial, since they are able to foster a good research culture and practices, support researchers in their career progression, and provide the motivation needed to continue and expand their work. The importance of such mechanisms has been widely recognized by research recognition and assessment experts and supported by key initiatives like the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment ([CoARA](#)) that actively work to encourage national and institutional administrative bodies to adopt these mechanisms, as their implementation remains insufficient in the current landscape.

The concepts of **credit**, **recognition and rewards** in scientific research are highly interconnected and are often used interchangeably and inconsistently in the literature. Therefore, before delving into the respective landscape, we should first provide the definitions we have adopted for the current report.

Credit refers to the *formal* attribution of roles and contributions to individuals who have participated in research activities or in generating research outputs. This may include authorship in publications or acknowledgement of contribution in other types of research outputs (e.g., research data and software) and activities (e.g., training). Taxonomies such as [CRediT](#) have been standardised to support describing the role of each author in a research output.

Recognition encompasses the broader acknowledgement of a researcher's achievements and contributions to their field. This includes awards, honours, citations, and public commendations that highlight a researcher's impact. Recognition extends beyond formal credit to include informal and community-wide acknowledgement, enhancing a researcher's reputation and career prospects.

Rewards are the (usually tangible) benefits that researchers receive in return for their contributions sustaining motivation and providing the necessary resources for continued research efforts. These can include financial incentives, academic positions, promotions, grants, and other forms of career advancement.

It is evident from the above that we assume there is a pathway for acknowledging research activities which starts with formally crediting researchers' contributions, progresses to gaining wider recognition, and results in materialising this recognition in the form of rewards. It is also worth mentioning that, in this report, the term "*acknowledgement*" is used as an umbrella term encompassing the concepts of credit, recognition, and reward. Figure 1 is summarising the respective concept.

Figure 1. Credit, recognition, and awards forming a pathway for acknowledging research activities.

Essentially, the aforementioned concepts play a crucial role in *research assessment* and monitoring practices. Credit, recognition, and reward mechanisms are key parts of any research assessment framework supporting informed decisions and enabling monitoring of quantitative and qualitative aspects of research. At the same time, they are central to the interventions aimed at reforming the current research assessment framework, a crucial step recognized in recent years for enhancing research culture and scientific impact (McKiernan et al., 2024 and Puebla et al., 2024).

In relevance to the required reform in research assessment, there are various challenges related to credit, recognition, and rewards in research that have been identified as vital. The most important one is related to the **need to properly acknowledge participation in a variety of diverse research-related activities beyond publications**. Nowadays, researchers engage in diverse activities that are integral to research including (among others) dataset creation, software development, training events, and educational material preparation. Incentivising diverse contributions encourages a holistic approach to research, striving for excellence, and cultivating a culture of appreciation in the scientific community. However, current practices may not uniformly recognize non-traditional research outputs like software engineering or training activities due to lack of standardisation (e.g., in citation practices) or other reasons. Institutions must align their evaluation processes with inclusive values, ensuring that faculty and departmental handbooks explicitly recognize non-traditional contributions as valid and worthy of reward.

Finally, there are other related challenges that are also relevant and of importance. Indicatively:

- *Recognition beyond indicators*. Traditional research assessment practices tend to over-rely on a limited set of quantitative indicators (e.g., citation counts, h-index), which are usually calculated without transparency and often prone to misinterpretation. In addition, over-relying to indicators often incentivises problematic research practices, a phenomenon commonly referred to as “Goodhart’s law” or “Campbell’s law”. In the context of research assessment, when researchers, institutions, or funding bodies focus excessively on specific indicators, these indicators risk being manipulated or

losing their original meaning. This leads to unintended consequences, such as fostering a “Publish-or-Perish” culture, encouraging superficial or incremental studies, and amplifying inequities in the research ecosystem. As a result, over-reliance on indicators can distort research practices and undermine the very qualities these metrics are meant to evaluate. Finally, over-relying on indicators may hinder inclusivity in assessment, focusing only on aspects that can be measured failing to consider other important and diverse contributions. For those reasons, a shift to a more comprehensive approach is needed—one that considers the diverse aspects and merits of research work while incorporating qualitative evidence using quantitative information only for supporting reasons.

- *Transparency and openness in crediting and assessment.* Research crediting and assessment systems often rely on indicators and evidence derived from proprietary data sources that are locked behind paywalls. This lack of openness undermines the transparency of the assessment process and prevents the research community from independently scrutinizing findings or offering alternative interpretations of the data. As a result, there is a pressing need for the further development and improvement of Open Infrastructures that provide metadata and services related to the wide range of research activities, ensuring that all contributions are acknowledged and valued. At the same time, those Open Infrastructures must offer the potential for customization, allowing institutions to adapt the framework to reflect their unique values, vision, and needs (INORMS, 2023). As we move towards a more open and transparent research culture, it is imperative to prioritize systems that fairly credit and recognize all forms of scholarly contributions, ensuring that researchers receive acknowledgement that is as comprehensive and inclusive as the work they undertake. This focus on credit and recognition is essential for translating abstract values such as accessibility, equity, and quality into improved behaviours and practices within the research community.

3 Methodology

In this section, we elaborate on the approach we have followed to conduct the analysis that resulted in the current report. In addition, we are discussing the limitations of this analysis.

The analysis conducted for this report followed a phased approach. In the *first phase*, we invited experts from the project consortium to compile an initial set of resources relevant to the fields of credit, recognition, and reward. No specific criteria were imposed on the type of resources to be provided; instead, we encouraged the experts to share any materials they deemed pertinent based on their fields of expertise. We have also asked the experts to provide material related to credit, recognition, and reward in general, without limiting their scope related to research software development and training activities. However, we requested that they indicate whether they believed the respective materials were relevant to these types of activities.

Upon completing this phase, we moved to the *second phase*, where the collected resources were reviewed and classified into distinct categories. After thorough evaluation of the provided material, we decided to organize the resources into three main categories:

- *Initiatives*, comprising collective efforts or organized movements aimed at addressing a specific issue, driving change, or advancing a particular cause in the field of credit, recognition, and reward
- *Standards*, referring to formalised guidelines, protocols, or specifications established to ensure consistency, compatibility, and quality in processes, systems, or products related to credit, recognition, and reward, and
- *Platforms*, including tools and services that enable or facilitate credit, recognition, and reward processes.

This classification scheme formed the basis for the initial list of resources collected.

In the *final phase*, we delved deeper into each resource, providing detailed descriptions, and extended the resource list through a resource-chaining approach. The aforementioned classification scheme formed the basis for organising and presenting the full list of resources collected in a concrete and intuitive way. The comprehensive list of resources compiled during this process is presented in the next sections and summarised in the tables included in Appendix A.

4 Initiatives on credit, recognition, and rewards

The following paragraphs present well-established initiatives aiming to address challenges related to crediting, recognition, and rewarding in research. Most of these initiatives are not specifically focused on research software and training, however they offer relevant recommendations and guidelines, even implicitly. For each initiative we first outline its overall objectives, contributions, and activities and then, discuss all subjects related to research software development and training. The first subsections (4.1-4.6) elaborate some key initiatives specifically focused on credit and recognition (sorted chronologically). Section 4.7 summarises various relevant initiatives by key funding organisations, focusing on the European Commission (EC), while Section 4.8 discusses related activities by community-driven organisations, like the Research Data Alliance (RDA).

4.1 The Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)

The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)¹ was established on December 12, 2012, during the Annual Meeting of The American Society for Cell Biology (ASCB) to address the pressing need for improving the ways in which scientific research outputs are evaluated. DORA emphasises the importance of evaluating research based on its intrinsic merit rather than relying on journal impact factors or other journal-based metrics. The initiative calls for a broader range of assessment criteria, encouraging the use of diverse qualitative and quantitative measures to ensure a more accurate and fair evaluation of scientific work.

Overall DORA's main objectives include raising awareness of new tools and responsible metrics use, facilitating the implementation of fair policies for hiring, promotion, funding, and catalysing global and interdisciplinary change in research assessment. It also aims to improve equity by addressing structural inequalities within academia. DORA supports these goals through community engagement, the development of resources, strategic partnerships, advising, and organising events to drive systemic change. By promoting transparency and accountability, DORA seeks to create a more inclusive and equitable environment for scientific research and academic progression.

In alignment with DORA's principles, institutions can adopt more inclusive and equitable assessment criteria that recognise and reward contributions in research software and training activities. More than 21K individuals and 3K organisations in 165 countries have signed DORA (McKiernan, E. et al., 2024). Promoting the use of qualitative and/or quantitative measures, DORA encourages a broader perspective on valuable scientific contributions, while acknowledging the critical role that research software and training play in advancing science.

Furthermore, in 2021 DORA launched the TARA² (Tools to Advance Research Assessment) project, aimed to support the development of new policies and practices for research assessment. In this context, an array of practical tools was introduced, including a Resource Library³, a collection of related materials (e.g., tools, reports), and Reformscape⁴, a searchable

¹ The DORA Declaration: <https://sfdora.org/>

² TARA project: <https://sfdora.org/project-tara/>

³ DORA's Resource Library: <https://sfdora.org/resource-library/>

⁴ DORA's Reformscape: <https://sfdora.org/reformscape/>

collection of criteria and standards for hiring, review, promotion, and tenure from academic institutions.

Particularly in recognising research software development and training efforts within the scientific community, the signatories of DORA support the adoption of specific practices, not only from institutions, funders, and organisations side, but in order to change the narrative, from all perspectives, researchers included.

4.2 Leiden Manifesto

The Leiden Manifesto⁵ provides a framework of ten principles for responsible research metrics. Developed by a group of experts, these principles aim to improve the use of quantitative metrics in research evaluation. The manifesto emphasises transparency, diversity, and the contextual understanding of metrics. It advocates for the inclusion of qualitative indicators alongside quantitative ones and calls for measures that support a range of research outputs and activities (Hicks D. et al., 2015).

The Leiden Manifesto authors identified a set of principles to ensure that research metrics are used responsibly, recognizing the diversity and complexity of research activities and outputs.

The ten principles are outlined below:

1. Quantitative evaluation should support qualitative, expert assessment.
2. Measure performance against the research missions of the institution, group or researcher.
3. Protect excellence in locally relevant research.
4. Keep data collection and analytical processes open, transparent and simple.
5. Allow those evaluated to verify data and analysis.
6. Account for variation by field in publication and citation practices.
7. Base assessment of individual researchers on a qualitative judgement of their portfolio.
8. Avoid misplaced concreteness and false precision.
9. Recognize the systemic effects of assessment and indicators.
10. Scrutinise indicators regularly and update them.

Since 2015 and its publication, numerous institutions in the U.S.A., Canada and Europe have promoted the principles within the Leiden Manifesto, while at the same time, it laid the foundations for the research assessment reform by the European Commission and other international bodies (McKiernan et al., 2024).

The Leiden Manifesto authors acknowledge that research metrics offer valuable insights that may be challenging to obtain or interpret through individual expertise alone. However, they

⁵ The Leiden Manifesto: <http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/>

emphasise that this quantitative data should remain a tool for assessment rather than becoming the objective itself. Effective decisions integrate solid statistics with an understanding of the research's purpose and context. Both quantitative and qualitative evidence play essential roles, each offering its own form of objectivity. Scientific decision-making should rely on rigorous processes guided by the best available data.

Research software and researchers' training activities evaluation, if complying with these ten principles, would positively affect the development of science and its interactions with society. In considering these approaches, Winter (2022) proposes using altmetrics alongside citations to provide a more comprehensive view of research impact. Konkiel, Sugimoto, and Williams (2016) highlight that altmetrics measure broader impact of research, for example on public policy and culture, and encompass diverse outputs such as code, reports, and datasets. They propose this new metrics for promotion and tenure decisions. However, they emphasize that quantitative metrics alone cannot fully capture research impact, leaving room for ongoing discussion.

4.3 The Hong Kong principles for assessing researchers

The Hong Kong Principles (HKPs)⁶, introduced in 2020, constitute a pivotal framework designed to elevate research integrity and ethical conduct in the global academic community. Developed through a collaborative effort involving international stakeholders from academia and research governance, these principles aim to transcend conventional metrics such as publication counts and journal impact factors in the evaluation of researchers. Their fundamental objective is to advocate for a comprehensive assessment approach that emphasises the quality, transparency, and societal relevance of scholarly contributions, thereby fostering a more equitable and robust research environment.

Similarly to DORA and the Leiden Manifesto, the HKPs highlight issues with quantitative metrics (e.g. publications, citations count), providing critical feedback on how these metrics are ill-suited (McKiernan et al., 2024) for evaluating several other aspects, as rigour and public involvement in research. The HKP paper presents notable examples of institutions recognizing broader research contributions beyond publications, including training and skills gained from mentoring and peer review. These examples include the University of Glasgow, the University of Exeter, and the Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity (TENK). All three institutions lead by example in career progression by implementing specific criteria: The University of Glasgow recognizes researchers for peer review and editorial contributions (mandating PIDs and DOIs), the University of Exeter developed a hub for mentoring and research knowledge dissemination (Exeter Academic), and TENK introduced a CV template with a dedicated mentoring work section.

Central to the HPKs is the promotion of fair and transparent evaluation criteria that acknowledge diverse facets of research excellence, including Open Science⁷ practices, interdisciplinary collaboration, and engagement with broader societal impacts. By encouraging

⁶ The Hong Kong Principles:

<https://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article?id=10.1371/journal.pbio.3000737>

⁷ Open Science: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

institutions and funding bodies to endorse these principles, the initiative seeks to mitigate prevalent issues such as research misconduct, publication bias, and undue reliance on quantitative metrics in academic evaluations. Nevertheless, the implementation of these principles poses challenges such as overcoming entrenched academic practices, ensuring consistency across diverse disciplines, and providing adequate support for researchers to align with these progressive evaluation standards.

In essence, the HPKs represent a significant advancement towards cultivating a research culture grounded in integrity, equity, and the responsible dissemination of knowledge. They underscore a collective commitment to enhancing the credibility and reliability of scientific research outputs globally, thereby fortifying the foundation of scholarly inquiry and innovation in the modern era.

4.4 The Hidden REF

The Hidden REF⁸ initiative, is a volunteer-led campaign, highlighting the large number of contributions to research that are usually hidden from traditional academic structures. The motivation for this initiative was that the vast majority of outputs submitted in the context of the Research Excellence Framework (REF) in 2008, 2014 and 2021 were journal and book publications leaving other types of important research contributions unrecognised. In response, the Hidden REF was established to recognize and celebrate the crucial roles and outputs of individuals that fall outside these categories.

Since its launch, Hidden REF has organized initiatives to showcase and reward these contributions, demonstrating their significance in supporting high-quality research. Among its most impactful activities is the organisation of competitions⁹ designed to highlight invisible contributions. These competitions have attracted a significant number of submissions from a large number of UK institutions, representing a diverse range of roles and outputs. Submissions have included everything from community engagement projects to open-source tools, as well as numerous other unseen yet vital contributions that underpin the research process. Hidden REF also organised a festival¹⁰ that brought together people who work in non-traditional research roles alongside policy makers, publishers and others involved in the research assessment.

Although the Hidden REF does not exclusively focus on acknowledging research software and training activities, these types of contributions are often highlighted as examples of the “hidden” work that goes unrecognised. Consequently, the recognition of software and training activities is both actively supported and frequently discussed at relevant events, reflecting their importance in fostering a more inclusive approach to research acknowledgement.

⁸ The Hidden REF: <https://hidden-ref.org/about/>

⁹ Hidden REF Competitions: <https://hidden-ref.org/hidden-ref-competition/>

¹⁰ The Festival of Hidden REF: <https://hidden-ref.org/festival-of-hidden-ref/>

4.5 HELIOS Open

On March 31, 2022, the inaugural convening of Higher Education Leadership Initiative for Open Scholarship (HELIOS Open¹¹), brought together presidents and senior leadership from 65 higher education institutions to advance the initiative's mission of promoting open scholarship practices. HELIOS Open is an initiative focused on fostering collective action among academic institutions to promote open scholarship (meaning “open science” or “open research”) practices. It aims to align research practices with the values of transparency, accessibility and inclusivity. One of HELIOS’s core objectives is to enhance how research contributions, particularly those involving research software and training activities are recognised and further awarded within academia.

HELIOS encourages the development and implementation of frameworks that support open science. These frameworks are designed to ensure that diverse forms of scholarly outputs, including software development, data curation, and educational activities, receive appropriate credit and are factored into evaluations for reappointment, promotions, tenure, and other career advancement related mechanisms. This initiative emphasises the importance of creating policies and guidelines that are adaptable across institutions, allowing them to reflect their unique missions and values while promoting a more inclusive approach to scholarly recognition.

Currently, based on information retrieved from the [HELIOS Open](https://www.heliosopen.org/) website (date of retrieval: 30.01.2025) there are 210 American universities and colleges (members). By participating in HELIOS, institutions (academic or not), commit to revisiting and reforming their evaluation criteria to better acknowledge and reward the full spectrum of research contributions, thereby helping to shift the academic culture towards greater openness and collaboration.

4.6 Coalition for Reforming Research Assessment (CoARA)

Among the most recent advances was the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)¹², which launched and published its agreement in 2022. CoARA is dedicated to improving research assessment practises through a global coalition of research funding organisations, research-performing institutions, assessment authorities, and learned societies. The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA), which CoARA supports, establishes a common framework for reforming research assessment to maximise the quality and impact of research while respecting the autonomy of individual organisations. The [ARRA's 10 commitments](#) serve as a foundation for guiding and implementing systemic changes in how research and researchers are evaluated. These commitments include principles, a clear timeline for reforms, and mechanisms for collaboration and mutual learning among stakeholders.

The ten commitments are outlined below:

¹¹ HELIOS Open: <https://www.heliosopen.org/>

¹² CoARA: <https://coara.eu/>

1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.
4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment.
5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to.
6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes.
7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.
8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.
9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.

One of the commitments is focusing on facilitating changes in assessment practices to enable recognition of the broad diversity of contributions, practices, and activities. In that context, CoARA acknowledges that research outputs beyond publications and related activities are relevant and extremely valuable. Teaching, leadership, supervision, training and mentoring are types of activities specifically mentioned. The role of a software engineer is provided as an indicative example of a role that should be recognised. In addition, the importance of practices that contribute to robustness, openness, transparency, and the inclusiveness of research is highlighted.

CoARA is supported by over 700 organisations from more than 40 countries. Moreover, CoARA has established a series of working groups, which are key communities of practice that work to implement research assessment reform in specific thematic areas. Those working groups are expected to produce valuable recommendations that should be considered by any initiative related to credit, recognition, and rewards in research.

4.7 Initiatives by Funding Organisations

In recent years, numerous research-funding organizations have taken significant steps toward adopting more responsible and inclusive frameworks for credit, recognition, and research assessment. For instance, the Wellcome Trust (UK) revised its grant assessment criteria to emphasize the quality and significance of research over publication metrics, such as journal

impact factors. Applicants are now required to provide evidence of their contributions to research culture, leadership, and public engagement, in addition to their scientific achievements. Similarly, the National Institutes of Health (NIH, US) has integrated DORA principles into its policies, discouraging the use of journal-based metrics (e.g., impact factor) in evaluating research contributions. Instead, the NIH focuses on the content, impact, and significance of the scientific work itself. In addition to such individual efforts, there are also collaborative initiatives, such as the creation of AGORRA¹³, a Global Observatory of Responsible Research Assessment, which brings together stakeholders from around the world to promote and accelerate the adoption of responsible research assessment practices. These efforts are often inspired by global initiatives like DORA and CoARA, or they emerge as responses to the growing call for reform driven by these initiatives. Together, they reflect a collective movement toward creating more equitable and inclusive research ecosystems.

The **European Commission (EC)** has put significant focus towards reforming research assessment practices, with the goal of fostering greater diversity, transparency, and quality in how research is evaluated across the EU. Following its signing the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment¹⁴ (ARRA), EC published an action plan¹⁵ to implement the commitments outlined in the Agreement and enable the required reforms in the current research assessment framework. At the same time, the EC Report on Research Assessment (European Research Executive Agency, 2024) was published discussing EC's plans in more detail, addressing also the contributions of European research projects to the reform of research assessment practices.

The European Open Science Cloud¹⁶ (EOSC), which provides a federated infrastructure designed to facilitate scientific data and information discoverability, is expected to play a key role in advancing these activities. Its ecosystem offers valuable tools and resources to support and enhance research assessment practices. To drive these efforts forward, the EC provides dedicated funding for Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC projects, focusing on establishing an operational, open, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) EOSC ecosystem. An indicative list of such projects, at the time of writing, includes:

- *GraspOS¹⁷ (1/2023-12/2025)*: GraspOS aims to design, evaluate, and implement an open, trusted, and federated infrastructure to support and enable policy reforms for Open-Science-aware and responsible research assessment. The project offers several key contributions in this context. First, GraspOS has conducted a comprehensive review to identify approaches, tools, and services for responsible research assessment that address Open Science principles. This review strengthens the evidence base needed to support systemic reforms and drive organizational change. Moreover, the project is developing a responsible research assessment framework that incorporates Open Science principles, providing guidance for both organizational and system-level practices. Finally, GraspOS' infrastructure includes tools and services designed to support Open-Science-aware and responsible

¹³ AGORRA: <https://researchonresearch.org/project/agorra/>

¹⁴ ARRA: <https://coara.eu/agreement/the-agreement-full-text/>

¹⁵ [Action Plan to implement the ten commitments outlined in the Agreement](#)

¹⁶ EOSC: <https://eosc.eu/>

¹⁷ GraspOS: <https://graspos.eu/>

assessment practices, contributing to the broader ecosystem of infrastructure, tools, and services for research assessment.

- *EVERSE*¹⁸ (3/2024-2/2027): The EVERSE project aims to establish a framework for research software and code excellence, collaboratively developed and endorsed by research communities. Its vision includes building a European network dedicated to Research Software Quality and laying the groundwork for a future Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence. The project places a strong emphasis on addressing the foundational changes required to ensure that activities related to research software development and training are appropriately acknowledged and recognized. Through these efforts, EVERSE seeks to elevate the status of research software and its creators within the broader research ecosystem, fostering a culture of quality, recognition, and innovation.
- *SciLake*¹⁹ (1/2023-12/2025): SciLake introduces the concept of the Open Scientific Lake, a modular ecosystem of components designed to facilitate easy data access, enhance knowledge discovery, improve research reproducibility, and support other research-related activities. The platform provides a highly customizable environment, allowing domain experts to select and tailor components to meet their specific needs. SciLake's capabilities can indirectly support crediting software activities by providing indicators of software usage. These metrics can be leveraged to appropriately credit researchers involved in developing and maintaining the software, thereby promoting recognition of their contributions.
- *Skills4EOSC*²⁰ (9/2022-8/2025): Skills4EOSC aims to create a unified training ecosystem for Open and FAIR science, visioning to establish a pan-European network of competence centres to enhance research training and scientific data management. The project maps Open Science career profiles, defines essential skills, and ensures quality learning materials. It integrates Open Science fundamentals into academic curricula and supports lifelong learning through professional networks. Collaboration models between national, regional, and international research infrastructures are developed to provide specialised training. Skills4EOSC also fosters stakeholder engagement, promotes certification frameworks, and builds partnerships for long-term sustainability.
- *OSTrails*²¹ (2/2024-1/2027): OSTrails aims to improve the way we plan, track, and assess scientific knowledge by enhancing existing systems and fostering collaboration across countries and themes. By integrating FAIR principles, Data Management Plans (DMP), and Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKG), OSTrails seeks to standardise and streamline research assessment, making it more transparent and efficient. This approach will improve the connectivity between research outputs and their impact, ensuring that scientific contributions are evaluated beyond traditional metrics like citations. Working with key players in research and innovation (R&I), OSTrails will set new standards for data management and FAIR assessment tools, promoting a more

¹⁸ EVERSE: <https://everse.software/>

¹⁹ SciLake: <https://scilake.eu/>

²⁰ Skills4EOSC: <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/>

²¹ OSTrails: <https://ostrails.eu/>

open and practical system for European scientific research. Ultimately, it will strengthen the way research is assessed, ensuring that findings are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, while also fostering collaboration and innovation across disciplines.

Moreover, in addition to the previous EOSC-related projects, the EC has funded other Horizon Europe relevant projects that contribute to the reform including:

- *OPUS*²² (9/2022-8/2025): OPUS is dedicated to reforming the assessment of research and researchers by promoting Open Science practices. This project conducts a comprehensive review of existing initiatives and develops interventions for Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPOs and RFOs). It establishes realistic indicators and metrics to track Open Science adoption and tests them through pilot action plans. A stakeholder-driven feedback loop ensures continuous refinement and validation. OPUS synthesises its findings into policy briefs and an updated OS-CAM2 framework, driving long-term change in research and researchers' assessment.
- *PathOS*²³ (9/2022-8/2025): PathOS aims to collect concrete evidence of Open Science (OS) effects, study the pathways of Open Science practices, from input to output, outcome and impact, including the consideration of enabling factors and key barriers. This project develops quantitative and qualitative methodologies to assess OS benefits and collaborates with stakeholders to refine impact indicators. PathOS activities include creating conceptual frameworks, integrating diverse data sources, conducting case studies, and ensuring policy relevance. Identifying OS practices' influence on research, innovation, and society, PathOS supports evidence-based policymaking and promotes the broader adoption of Open Science across Europe.
- *ELIXIR-STEERS*²⁴ (2/2024-1/2027): ELIXIR-STEERS is a project designed to help life science researchers access national datasets and perform large-scale, cross-border data analyses. The project promotes best practices in software management and supports life scientists in developing robust, reproducible and energy-efficient software and workflows. ELIXIR-STEERS, will compile these practices into a dedicated tool-kit to enhance sustainability in computational research. Embedding common standards across ELIXIR Nodes, this project facilitates seamless data analyses across Europe. This project fosters international collaborations to ensure global competitiveness and long-term sustainability in life science research. *Finally, there are also dedicated tasks on credit and recognition.*
- TIER2²⁵: TIER2 aims at enhancing trust, integrity, and efficiency in research by improving the reproducibility of scientific results. This project investigates reproducibility across social, life, and computer sciences, as well as research publishers and funders, to develop tailored interventions. Through co-creation with these communities, TIER2 examines epistemological, social, and technical factors affecting reproducibility, builds an evidence base on existing practices, and develops

²² OPUS: <https://opusproject.eu/>

²³ PathOS: <https://pathos-project.eu/>

²⁴ ELIXIR-STEERS: <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/steers>

²⁵ TIER2: <https://tier2-project.eu/>

new tools using scenario-planning and user-centred design. By increasing research re-usability and quality, TIER2 strengthens trust and integrity in the European Research Area (ERA) and the global Research & Innovation system. The project has dedicated activities on software reproducibility and relevant indicators.

Returning to EOSC, the association has also established dedicated Task Forces (TFs) and Expert Groups to enrich and coordinate the activities of the EOSC-related projects. These initiatives play a pivotal role in advancing specific aspects of EOSC's mission by harnessing specialized expertise and fostering collaboration within the research community. In relevance to the field of credit, recognition, and rewards (with a focus on research software development and training) EOSC has established the following TFs and expert groups:

- **EOSC Task Force on “Research careers, recognition and credit”²⁶**. This TF was established in the context of EOSC-A Task Forces 2021-2023 in the “Research careers and curricula” area and focused on enhancing the recognition of research careers providing recommendations and frameworks for recognizing research contributions. Specifically, the TF aimed to develop relevant specifications, guidelines, and best practices advocating for Open Science principles and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration. The main outputs of the group were a position paper describing how EOSC can enable the research assessment reform (Nilsonne G. et al., 2023) and a joint report (together with the three other TFs in the “Research careers and curricula” area) to outline their joint efforts in designing strategies that empower research intermediaries to adopt, implement, and promote Open Science in European research (van Gelder C. W. G. et al., 2024).
- **EOSC Task Force on “Data stewardship curricula and career paths”²⁷**. This TF was established in the context of EOSC-A Task Forces 2021-2023 in the “Research careers and curricula” area and focused on the Data Stewards role and their core activities. In this context, credit and recognition for data stewardship and training activities was taken into consideration. The main outputs of the group were two recommendation documents related to data stewardship related careers (Kalová, T. et al. 2024 and Basalti, C. et al. 2024) and a joint report with the other three TFs in the “Research careers and curricula” area (van Gelder C. W. G. et al., 2024).
- **EOSC Task Force on “Infrastructures for Quality Research Software”²⁸**. This TF was established in the context of EOSC-A Task Forces 2021-2023 with the aim to foster the development and deployment of tools and services that allow researchers to properly archive, reference, describe with proper metadata, share and reuse research software, as well as to improve their quality, both from the technical and organizational point of view. Although this TF did not consider the credit and recognition subject, it provided useful context for developing credit and recognition frameworks that consider software contributions. The TF produced various relevant reports: Courbebaisse G. et al. (2023) outlined the phases of the research software life-cycle concluding with recommendations on EOSC infrastructure components needed to support these processes and platforms; Azzouz-Thuderoz, M. et al. (2023) presents a detailed gap

²⁶ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/research-careers-recognition-and-credit/>

²⁷ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/data-stewardship-curricula-and-career-paths>

²⁸ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/infrastructures-quality-research-software>

analysis of the current infrastructures supporting research software within EOSC; finally, David, M. et al. (2024a, 2024b) provided an overview on research software quality characteristics and best practices for ensuring software quality, respectively.

- **Expert Group on Opportunity Area 5²⁹ (“Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition, and Upscaling”)**. Focused on advancing skills, training, rewards, recognition and up-scaling within the EOSC, the group aims to deepen collaboration among consortia of EOSC projects, EOSC Association and the mission of the European Commission (EC), in the context of implementing the EOSC European Partnership and its Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). This group will further address and review key challenges in skills development, and explore strategies for enhancing frameworks, recognition mechanisms and workforce up-scaling. All efforts of the OA5 Expert Group, are in support of the EOSC’s goal of an operational, federated infrastructure for FAIR data sharing across disciplines and borders.
- **Expert Group on Opportunity Area 7³⁰ “Research Software”**. The EOSC Experts Opportunity Area 7 (OA7) focuses on advancing research software within the EOSC framework, recognising its crucial role as a tool, research outcome, and object. This expert group addresses challenges in curation, quality, preservation, metadata, registries, and reproducibility, ensuring best practices for both researchers who code and Research Software Engineers (RSEs). A key priority is credit and recognition for software developers to promote sustainable software practices. Building on prior EOSC efforts, the OA7 Expert Group collaborates with global initiatives such as SciCodes, RDA FAIR4RS, and ReSA, fostering an Open Science culture that elevates research software to a first-class citizen in science.

4.8 Community-driven Initiatives

In this section, we explore community-driven initiatives focused on credit, recognition, and rewards. We begin by examining activities led by community-driven organizations, such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA), and conclude with individual efforts made by members of the broader research community.

The **Research Data Alliance (RDA)**³¹ is a community-driven initiative dedicated to facilitating the open sharing and reuse of research data across disciplines and borders to tackle global challenges. Organised into Working Groups (WGs) and Interest Groups (IGs)³² RDA convenes experts from academia, industry, and government to develop consensus-based solutions that promote data interoperability, standardisation, and best practices in research data management and sharing. Some relevant RDA groups are the following:

- [Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO4RS\)](#). This WG was co-convened with the Research Software Alliance (ReSA) and aims to create a community of stakeholders involved in promoting and/or implementing policy that

²⁹ OA5: <https://eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa5-skills-training-rewards-recognition-upscaling/>

³⁰ OA 7: <https://eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa7-research-software/>

³¹ RDA: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-the-rda/>

³² RDA WGs and IGs: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/>

supports research software at the research institution level (e.g., universities, national laboratories).

- [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\)](#). This WG aimed to produce a set of FAIR principles for research software. The group published a relevant report (Chue Hong, N. P et al. 2022) that elaborates on the suggested principles.
- [Software Source Code IG](#). This IG aims to provide a forum to discuss issues on management, sharing, discovery, archival and provenance of software source code. It will pay special attention to source code that generates research data and plays an important role in scientific publications.

Moving to another initiative, in 2024, the Research Evaluation Recommendations Panel of **Informatics Europe**³³ and European National Informatics Associations³⁴ prepared a [draft report on Informatics Research Evaluation](#). This report aims to be a comprehensive update to previous reports from 2008 and 2018, refining and enhancing research evaluation practices within Informatics and aligning its recommendations with CoARA. The report emphasises disciplinary specificity, recognising Informatics as a unique case of mathematics, science, and engineering, and calls for evaluation methods that respect this interdisciplinary nature. Key aspects include the prominence of highly selective conferences in disseminating research, the growing trend of integrating conference papers and journals, and the rise of innovative publishing models, such as open archives and overlay journals. Artefact evaluation is highlighted as a crucial practice, recognising the impact of software, open datasets, and trained machine learning models. In addition, the report addresses Open Science practices, interdisciplinary research evaluation and the evolving role of artificial intelligence (AI) in research assessment. Overall, the report advocates for evaluation practices that acknowledge the distinctive characteristics of Informatics research, promoting responsible bibliometric use, appropriate credit assignment, and recognition of diverse research outputs, ensuring that assessment methods evolve in line with academic and technological advancements.

The work of the INORMS Research Evaluation Group (REG)³⁵, that was established in 2018 to consider how best to ensure that research evaluation is meaningful, responsible and effective is also important to be mentioned. Key activities of REG's members, representing the research management societies within INORMS, have focused on guiding senior university leaders and practitioners in adopting and implementing responsible research evaluation. The main output of the group regarding this was the creation of the [SCOPE Framework](#), a structured methodology for responsible research evaluation, designed to guide institutions in developing fair, transparent, and context-sensitive assessment practices. It consists of five key steps: Start with what you value, consider context, Options for measuring, Probe deeply, and Evaluate the evaluation. By prioritizing institutional values, considering the specific context of assessment, selecting appropriate metrics, critically examining biases and limitations, and continuously refining evaluation processes, SCOPE helps organizations implement research assessment that is both meaningful and responsible. It is widely recognized as a practical tool for aligning research evaluation with principles of openness, inclusivity, and integrity.

³³ Informatics Europe: <https://www.informatics-europe.org/>

³⁴ National Informatics Associations: <https://www.informatics-europe.org/policy/national-associations.html>

³⁵ INORMS REG: <https://inorms.net/research-evaluation-group/>

In an article published in 2022, the authors belonging to the **HuMetricsHSS Initiative** conducted research interviews across the **Big Ten Academic Alliance (BTAA)** as an extension of their previous work on values-enacted scholarly practice (Agate N. et al. 2022) The interviews focused on current systems of evaluation within BTAA institutions, the potential problems and inequalities of those processes, the kinds of scholarly work that could be better recognized and rewarded, and the contexts and pressures evaluators are under, including, as the process progressed, the onset and ongoing conditions of COVID-19. The interviews focused primarily on the reappointment, promotion, and tenure (RPT) process. Interviewees outlined a number of issues to be addressed, including toxicity in evaluation, scholars' increased alienation from the work they are passionate about, and a high-level virtue-signalling of values by institutions without the infrastructure or resources to support the enactment of those values. Based on these conversations, this white paper offers a set of recommendations for making wide scale change to address systematic injustice, erasure, and devaluation of academic labour in order to strengthen the positive public impact of scholarship.

On another initiative, in 2016, the **FORCE11**³⁶ software citation Working Group, published the [Software Citation Principles](#), a set of principles advocating for proper credit and attribution, unique identification, persistence, accessibility, and specificity in software citations. The principles emphasise the importance of research software, scholarly credit and legal attribution, the inclusion of a unique identification method (e.g. DOI) and of unique identifiers and metadata (persistence), the guaranteed accessibility and specificity (dates, versions). The report identifies potential issues that emerge from these principles, including concerns and questions around what software should be cited, how to handle the out-of-scope peer-review in the context of software citation principles (challenge of evaluating software credibility and quality, as it is often not formally peer-reviewed like research papers), or format inconsistency in reference lists.

Moreover, in 2023, **Science Europe**³⁷ published a report (Science Europe 2023) to set out a vision for future recognition systems and offers a collection of recommendations aimed at research organisations, and good practice examples that provide examples of possible directions for change at institutional level. Key recommendation provided included (among others) adopting the implementation of FAIR principles for services, developing standardized metadata schemas, ensuring the use of persistent identifiers, enhancing interoperability of the credit and recognition platforms of different domains, collaborating with researcher communities to better capture specialised needs, and enhancing transparency in the credit and recognition processes and platforms.

In 2023, the **Netherlands eScience Center released** a detailed [Job profile and Role description](#) for Research Software Engineers (RSEs), recognizing their vital contributions to scientific advancement. This initiative aims to better capture the work of RSEs, whose expertise ranges from academic research to software stewardship. By publishing these profiles, the centre hopes to standardise and promote recognition of RSEs in the academic community, encouraging other organizations to follow.

The **Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability** ([ADORE.software](#)) emphasises the critical role of software in research and highlights the

³⁶ FORCE11: <https://force11.org/>

³⁷ Science Europe: <https://www.scienceeurope.org/>

necessity of investing in its development and maintenance. By advocating for sustainable funding and support for research software and its developers, ADORE.software ensures that contributors receive proper recognition and credit for their work. This initiative promotes the reproducibility of research outcomes and underscores the importance of acknowledging the efforts of those who create and maintain essential research tools.

Finally, it is worth noting that individual research-performing institutions, often inspired by broader initiatives, have already begun updating their hiring, tenure, and promotion processes with the aim to recognize a wider range of research outputs beyond traditional journal publications, incorporating contributions such as data and software (Puebla et al., 2024). Indicatively, the Loyola University Chicago Department of English ([Guidelines for Promotion and Tenure](#)) and the University of Arizona ([Criteria by College](#)), outline specific guidelines for promotion and tenure, while institutions such as the University of Maryland (through DORA) and the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL; CoARA), include references to data and software in their hiring, tenure, and promotion criteria. In addition, the FASEB DataWorks! Prize (through HELIOS Open) recognises contributions related to data sharing or reuse. At the University of Calgary, the Knowledge Commons Network guidelines, ([Knowledge Commons Network](#)) emphasise the inclusion of data and software in appointment, promotion, tenure, and annual assessment processes. These guidelines suggest appointing a dedicated reviewer for data and software to ensure committee feedback appropriately considers such contributions.

Puebla et al. (2024) make a notable contribution by proposing specific guidelines for committee members assessing candidates' contributions to data and software. These guidelines include evaluating technical competency in data and software creation, management, and use, as well as innovation in the technology, design, or approaches employed. Additionally, service in professional organizations, journals, or committees promoting open practices is considered relevant, alongside contributions to teaching, training, outreach, and other community activities that advance best practices in open data and open-source software.

Another research by Alperin JP. et al., 2024, assessing 'The value of data and other non-traditional scholarly outputs in academic review, promotion, and tenure in Canada and the United States' studied 129 universities in the US and Canada. Among the 57 research-intensive institutions sampled, nine mentioned data and 37 mentioned research software recognition in their guidelines. In order to demonstrate that institutions value data and research software contributions, it is crucial to explicitly encourage candidates to include these contributions in their job applications and materials submitted for tenure and promotion reviews. Further, with regards to openness, Alperin JP. et al., 2024, recommended that after implementing a framework for recognizing data and software contributions, institutions should conduct a review to assess whether the process aligns with their values and identify any necessary adjustments. This review provides an opportunity to gather feedback from all participants in the process (including applicants and review committee members) and to evaluate how open data and software practices are evolving. This reflective process helps ensure that academic evaluation aligns with community best practices. Institutions are encouraged to share the results of implementing recognition for data and software in their evaluation processes with the broader community and to transparently discuss the challenges

of balancing the various dimensions of scholarly contributions considered by evaluation committees.

Standards and Platforms

In this section, we outline a variety of existing standards (Section 5.1) and platforms (Section 5.2) that are essential in the context of crediting, recognising, and rewarding research work.

4.9 Standards

In this section we discuss different standards that can be useful in the context of credit, recognition, and reward processes. By the term ‘standard’ we refer to a published, well-documented specification (e.g., a metadata schema) focusing mostly on cases that are well-established in the research community. The standards examined in this section are sorted in lexicographical order.

4.9.1 Common European Research Information Format (CERIF)

The [Common European Research Information Format \(CERIF\)](#) is a standardized data model designed for managing and exchanging research information across institutions, funders, and policy-makers. Developed by EuroCRIS, CERIF provides a structured, interoperable framework for integrating diverse research entities, including publications, projects, datasets, software, organizations, and funding. It enables semantic linking, ensuring meaningful connections between research outputs and metadata. Widely adopted by Current Research Information Systems (CRISs), CERIF facilitates efficient reporting, evaluation, and decision-making, supporting Open Science and fostering research transparency across Europe and beyond.

4.9.2 Citation File Format (CFF)

[Citation File Format](#) is a specification for a human- and machine-readable file that can be added to a code repository to inform viewers on the correct way to cite the respective software code. It can also be used for citing datasets. It is supported by various well-established platforms including GitHub, Gitlab, Zenodo, and Zotero. It promotes proper credit and citation practices.

4.9.3 CodeMeta

[CodeMeta](#) is a minimal metadata schema for the description of research software and code, in JSON and XML. The goal of CodeMeta is to create a concept vocabulary that can be used to standardize the exchange of software metadata across repositories and organizations. CodeMeta started by comparing the software metadata used across multiple repositories, which resulted in the [CodeMeta Metadata Crosswalk](#). That crosswalk was then used to generate a set of software metadata concepts, which were arranged into a JSON-LD context for serialization.

4.9.4 CRediT Taxonomy

The Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT)³⁸ was developed in 2015 in order to recognize the role of article contributors in a scientific publication. CRediT is a simple taxonomy of roles that

³⁸ CRediT : <https://credit.niso.org>

range from conceptualization and data curation to article writing and reviewing, experiment design and software development. Since 2022 CRediT has been approved as a NISO ANSI standard, and made available as part of the [Journal Publishing Tag Library](#) (JATS). More than two dozen different publishers now use it to distinguish the contributions of a scientific publication.

4.9.5 CODEOWNERS

[CODEOWNERS](#) is a special file type in GitHub, that is used to define individuals or teams responsible for specific files or directories within a code repository. Consequently, CODEOWNER files help maintain transparency in software development and maintenance and can be used to give proper recognition and accountability to contributors for their contributions.

4.9.6 Contributor Role Ontology (CRO)

[CRO](#) is an ontology that extends CRediT with more roles to provide transparency in contributions to scholarly published work, to enable improved systems of attribution, credit, and accountability. It includes roles related to research software and training activities.

4.9.7 DataCite's contributorTypes

[DataCite](#)'s schema of metadata properties, includes a property named "Contributor" which refers to the institution or person responsible for collecting, managing, distributing, or otherwise contributing to the development of a resource. This property has a sub-property called "[contributorType](#)" which captures the type of contribution of the contributor and its values come from a controlled vocabulary including more than twenty distinct roles.

4.9.8 Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI)

The [Dublin Core](#) standard offers a simplified set of metadata elements applicable to a wide range of resources, including educational content. Its elements, like creator, subject, and date, support basic resource description and enhance interoperability.

4.9.9 GraspOS API specification

The [GraspOS API specification](#) is designed to facilitate data exchange and interoperability between services that provide (meta)data valuable for the implementation of research assessment processes and relevant value-added services. It is built upon an extension of the Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF), called RA-SKG.

4.9.10 INRIA's Taxonomy for Software Contributions

Software is a key component of modern research across disciplines, yet proper citation and authorship remain complex due to various roles in its development. [This paper](#) discusses relevant matters and introduces a new Taxonomy for Software Contributions.

4.9.11 OpenAIRE Guidelines

The [OpenAIRE Guidelines](#) is a set of interoperability guidelines to help repository managers expose publications, datasets and CRIS metadata via the OAI-PMH protocol in order to integrate with the [OpenAIRE infrastructure](#). OpenAIRE Guidelines have been released for publication repositories, data archives, CRIS systems, software repositories and repositories of other research products.

4.9.12 Open Badges

[Open Badges](#) is a globally recognized format for issuing and managing digital badges that represent verifiable skills and achievements. These badges are portable and can be shared across platforms, allowing individuals to showcase their accomplishments. Open Badges can be used by learners to collect and display their credentials, by issuers to recognize proficiency, and by developers to create interoperable tools. The ecosystem fosters a way to formally recognize micro-credentials and track skill development.

4.9.13 OpenSSF Badges

The [OpenSSF Best Practices Badge](#) programme is designed to help open source software projects demonstrate their adherence to security and quality best practices. Projects can self-certify by answering a set of criteria, and automated analysis ensures accurate assessments. The badge highlights projects that follow recommended practices, providing greater visibility and trust to consumers. This initiative, part of the [Open Source Security Foundation \(OpenSSF\)](#), aims to improve the security and sustainability of open-source software.

4.9.14 Scholarly Contributions and Roles Ontology (SCoRo)

The [Scholarly Contributions and Roles Ontology \(SCoRo\)](#) is an ontology which helps authors, publishers, and research administrators describe contributions and roles in scholarly work. SCoRo defines roles in relation to journal articles, research activities, and broader academic contexts. The ontology uses present-tense object properties and class individuals to represent roles and contributions that may apply to past, present, or future scenarios. Since roles vary by context and time, SCoRo incorporates the time-indexed value in context (TVC) pattern from the [Publishing Roles Ontology \(PRO\)](#). This approach enables structured representation of roles within specific time-frames, ensuring clarity in scholarly contributions.

4.9.15 Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF)

The [Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework \(SKG-IF\)](#) is a metadata standard aimed at enhancing the interoperability of Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). SKG-IF provides a lingua franca for SKGs, ensuring that diverse research entities including publications, datasets, software, projects, and organisations can be consistently represented and connected across platforms. By facilitating seamless data integration and knowledge discovery, SKG-IF supports Open Science principles, improving the accessibility, transparency, and re-usability of scholarly metadata across different research infrastructures.

4.9.16 The Software Credit Taxonomy

The [Software Credit Taxonomy](#) is a taxonomy for the different roles that an individual can have in a software project.

4.10 Platforms

In this section, we present various platforms supporting the credit, recognition, and reward of research work. The platforms are sorted in lexicographical order.

4.10.1 APICURON

[APICURON](#) is a database designed to credit and acknowledge the contributions of researchers by tracking and aggregating their activities across multiple knowledge bases and platforms. It addresses the critical need for recognizing diverse contributions beyond traditional publications, including data curation, software development, and training material creation. APICURON functions by collecting and aggregating activity events from third-party resources, providing recognition to contributors through statistics, achievements, and leaderboards. This promotes a culture of acknowledgement and incentivises valuable contributions to scientific knowledge and data resources. Its flexible data model and API facilitate integration with existing platforms, allowing it to be adapted and extended to meet specific needs within initiatives like the EOSC Science Clusters and ELIXIR.

APICURON's key functionalities include:

- **Recognition and Credit Attribution**: APICURON can be used to track the activities of researchers and RSEs involved in developing and maintaining research software. By capturing and recording various activities, such as development tasks and training, APICURON ensures that these contributions are visible and quantifiable.
- **Aggregating Data**: By aggregating data from different sources, APICURON can provide a comprehensive overview of an individual's contributions across multiple projects and platforms. This helps in recognizing the diverse efforts of researchers and trainers.
- **Gamification and Engagement**: Implementing gamification concepts like badges and medals, APICURON can enhance engagement and motivation among researchers and trainers. These rewards can be used to acknowledge milestones and achievements in research software development and training activities. Moreover, leaderboards can promote healthy competition and provide public recognition for top contributors, further incentivising quality contributions.
- **Integration and Adaptation**: APICURON's flexible data model and API allow easy integration with existing platforms used in research software recognition initiatives. This ensures that recognition mechanisms can be adapted and extended to meet specific needs within the EOSC Science Clusters.
- **Customization**: The system's customizable nature allows it to define specific achievements and scoring systems relevant to different types of activities.

- **Reporting and Monitoring:** APICURON provides real-time tracking and reporting of curation activities, which can be used to actively monitor the contributions of researchers and trainers. This provides a transparent and reliable mechanism for recognition and career development.
- **Supporting Open Science:** By integrating with ORCID, APICURON ensures that the contributions are linked to individual researcher profiles, providing a persistent and recognized identifier for their work. This aligns with the broader goals of Open Science by making contributions more visible and attributable.

APICURON's capabilities in tracking, aggregating, and recognizing contributions through gamification and real-time monitoring make it a valuable tool for implementing a recognition framework for researchers and research software engineers involved in research software and training activities. This aligns well with the goals of promoting sustainable software practices and fostering a culture where research software is acknowledged as a vital component of the scientific process.

4.10.2 BadgEd (Open Digital Badges)

[BadgEd](#) is an open digital badge platform developed by the University of Edinburgh to recognize achievements in learning technology. It provides a way to award badges for skill development, which are verifiable and shareable across professional networks. The platform supports both traditional and non-traditional forms of learning, ensuring inclusivity and flexibility in recognizing educational milestones. By offering open digital badges, BadgEd enhances transparency and fosters motivation among learners.

4.10.3 BIP! Scholar

[BIP! Scholar](#) is a platform that enables researchers to create comprehensive profiles showcasing their research activities beyond scientific publications. By integrating data from scholarly knowledge graphs and ORCID, it provides custom reports with indicators that reflect productivity, impact, and career stage, while accounting for diverse roles using the CRediT taxonomy. The platform supports dynamic, customizable profiles with innovative templates like narrative CVs, fostering a more inclusive and responsible representation of research careers. BIP! Scholar highlights contributions across roles and activities, promoting recognition and transparency in research work.

4.10.4 DORA Reformscape

[Reformscape](#), developed by DORA, is an interactive tool designed to showcase global initiatives aimed at improving research assessment practices. By highlighting efforts to move beyond traditional metrics like journal impact factors, it promotes responsible and equitable evaluation of research contributions. The platform enables users to explore diverse policies and practices, fostering recognition of a wide range of research outputs and activities. Reformscape supports the advancement of inclusive and transparent assessment frameworks that value the full scope of scholarly contributions.

4.10.5 DORA Resource Library

The [Resource Library](#), developed by DORA, is a collection of materials to facilitate the development of responsible research and researcher assessment policies and practices.

4.10.6 ELIXIR's Training e-Support System (TeSS)

[ELIXIR TeSS](#) is a platform that aggregates training materials and events in the Life Sciences, using metadata to enhance discoverability. The [OSCARS mTeSS-X](#) project extends TeSS into a multi-tenant, distributed catalogue to overcome the fragmentation of training resources across Research Infrastructures and Science Clusters. Enabling federation and cross-instance content exchange, mTeSS-X will support tailored yet interconnected catalogues, fostering a more cohesive European research community. This innovation promotes FAIR and open training while breaking down barriers between thematic communities.

4.10.7 FAIR Software Checklist

The [FAIR Software Checklist](#) is a self-assessment wizard that can be used for the assessment of FAIRness of research software.

4.10.8 GraspOS Infrastructure

GraspOS infrastructure (<https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/>), an open infrastructure that aims to facilitate the implementation of policy reforms towards Open-Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment. The infrastructure aggregates and makes discoverable open resources, such as tools, services, datasets, guidance material that can catalyse the implementation of relevant policy reforms. The infrastructure is a key exploitable output of the GraspOS project (<https://graspos.eu/>), a Horizon Europe project with the objective to enhance the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem with components to pave the way towards Open-Science-aware, Responsible Research Assessment.

4.10.9 OERSI (Open Educational Resource Search Index)

[OERSI](#) is a search engine designed to connect users with free educational materials across various OER repositories. It aggregates metadata from distributed state initiatives, university repositories, and specialized subject repositories. OERSI does not store content but facilitates uniform searching of available resources. Developed as an open-source service, it integrates with other platforms and offers customizable search options. The platform operates openly, allowing community involvement in development and feedback via GitLab.

4.10.10 OpenAIRE Graph

The [OpenAIRE Graph](#) is a comprehensive scholarly knowledge graph that aggregates and connects metadata from diverse research outputs, including publications, datasets, software, projects, organizations, and other research-related entities. Developed by [OpenAIRE](#), it integrates data from trusted repositories, institutional archives, funders, and publishers, ensuring broad coverage and interoperability. The OpenAIRE Graph follows Open Science principles, enabling transparent and reproducible research by providing openly accessible, structured metadata. By linking research outputs and contextual information, it facilitates

advanced discovery, impact assessment, and policy monitoring, supporting researchers, institutions, and funders in navigating the evolving research landscape.

4.10.11 OpenAlex

[OpenAlex](#) is a free and open scholarly knowledge graph that aggregates and interconnects research outputs, including publications, authors, institutions, journals, and concepts. Designed as a fully open alternative to proprietary bibliographic databases, OpenAlex provides structured metadata that supports advanced research discovery, impact analysis, and bibliometric studies. It leverages open metadata sources, such as CrossRef, ORCID, and institutional repositories, ensuring broad accessibility and transparency.

4.10.12 OpenEBench Tools Observatory

The [OpenEBench Tools Observatory](#) is one of the services provided by the OpenEBench suite of platforms. Its aim is to help its users to explore trends in key aspects of research software including aspects related to FAIRness and performance.

4.10.13 OpenPlato

[OpenPlato](#) is an open platform designed to facilitate the discovery, sharing, and management of training resources for researchers and professionals in various scientific domains. It serves as a learning resource aggregator, providing access to courses, tutorials, and training materials while promoting collaborative learning and Open Science principles. OpenPlato supports metadata-driven discoverability, ensuring that training resources are well-structured, searchable, and reusable across different disciplines.

4.10.14 ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)

[ORCID](#) is a non-profit organization that supports useful services for researchers. It provides unique, persistent identifiers for researchers to ensure clear connections between their work and contributions. Additionally, it offers academic profile functionalities to researchers from all scientific domains. ORCID aims to improve transparency and trust in research by linking individuals to their affiliations and activities across disciplines. Through its services, including the ORCID iD and the Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), ORCID facilitates interoperability with other organisations, allowing researchers to manage and share their academic profiles globally.

4.10.15 Research Asset Repositories

Research asset repositories are digital platforms designed to store, organize, and share various research outputs, including publications, datasets, software, training materials, and other scholarly resources. These repositories serve as centralized hubs that facilitate open access, improve discoverability, and enhance the re-usability of research assets across disciplines. They often implement metadata standards and persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) to ensure proper citation, versioning, and long-term accessibility. Indicative examples include general repositories like [Zenodo](#), [ArXiv](#), and [HAL](#), code repositories like [Github](#) and [Gitlab](#), container image catalogs like [DockerHub](#), and workflow registries like the [WorkflowHub](#).

4.10.16 Research Software Encyclopedia (RSE)

[RSEncyclopedia](#) is a tool designed for research software engineers to better document and categorize their work using a specific taxonomy. It automatically aggregates data from existing software databases and allows users to interact with it by answering taxonomy-related questions via social media and chat. The platform also enables users to create static websites for their own research software.

4.10.17 Software Citation Station

This publicly available tool was introduced in 2024 (Wagg, T. et al. 2024) with the aim to streamline and standardize software citations in academic work. It allows users to quickly find or add software citations, promoting consistent acknowledgement of software contributions.

5 Towards a Framework for Crediting, Recognising and Rewarding Research Software and Training Activities

In this section, we outline a potential architecture that can support a framework for crediting, recognizing, and rewarding researchers for their contributions to research software development and training. This preliminary “sketch” builds on recommendations from related initiatives (Section 4) and leverages the relevant standards and platforms discussed (Section 5). Finally, it builds upon the work being done in the context of the OI4RRA CoARA working group (see Section 4.6) and relevant projects including GraspOS, OPUS, and ELIXIR-STEERS.

5.1 Key Points of a Potential Framework

To ensure crediting, recognition, and career progression for researchers that acknowledge research software and training activities, an updated policy framework should be designed and implemented. In this section, we summarise some key points that are important for the design of such a framework inspired by the recommendations made by the initiatives we have analysed in this report (Section 4) reflecting also some relevant requirements related to the implementation. In the next section, we provide more details on the implementation.

The most crucial characteristic of the needed research credit, recognition, and rewards framework is **inclusiveness**: it should accommodate a diverse range of research activities, including contributions related to research software engineering and training. This need is consistently emphasized in recommendations from relevant initiatives and in the respective literature. Traditionally, research credit and recognition systems have been almost exclusively based on publications. While cultural factors have played a role, practical limitations have also contributed to this focus since recognizing contributions beyond publications is challenging, leading to what is known as the “Lamppost Problem” where frameworks prioritize what is easy to measure and track rather than what is actually important.

To effectively implement a credit and recognition framework that integrates research software and training activities, various requirements must be met. First of all, there is a need for platforms that provide rich metadata, including persistent identifiers, for these types of contributions. Ideally, these platforms should be interoperable and follow common standards in exposing their metadata to ensure seamless metadata exchange. Moreover, there is a need for platforms that capture and maintain metadata on contributor-ship, linking researchers with their research software and training activities. Finally, templates for academic profiles should be developed to reflect these types of contributions and established academic profile platforms should adapt to incorporate them.

Another important issue that should be addressed by a credit and recognition framework is **standardisation in acknowledgement of usage**. The necessity for formal and unified ways to cite software and training activities, given the growing recognition of their critical role in advancing research and innovation, arises from the need to consider insights about their usage and impact during the credit and recognition process. For instance, the fact that a software package developed by some researchers is widely used or cited by many others in

the field, is important to be recognised. However, without a standardization on how software usage should be acknowledged within the research community, implementing effective mechanisms to track software impact will remain a challenge.

Finally, another important characteristic is **openness**: the implementation of the framework should be based on open data and sources (e.g., open Scientific Knowledge Graphs - SKGs) facilitating transparency in the evaluation process and other related activities. In recent years, a need for a shift towards the use of *Open Infrastructures (OIs)* that are transparent, equitable, and accessible to all stakeholders has been identified as important by various initiatives (the most important one being the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information³⁹). Such a transition is essential for aligning crediting, recognition, and assessment practices with the principles of *Open Science (OS)* and ensuring they serve the diverse needs of the global research community.

5.2 A Blueprint for the Implementation of the Framework

The credit and recognition framework previously outlined, designed to inclusively acknowledge diverse research activities and contributions focusing on software development and training, can largely be implemented by leveraging and properly adapting existing standards and platforms.

Regarding the standards, the following cases are important:

- **Software and training metadata standards.** Using common metadata standards that can be used by different sources to describe in detail researcher activities related to software and training, is very important for the implementation of a credit and recognition framework that will take into consideration this type of contributions by researchers. Any implementation should attempt to be inclusive by incorporating metadata records by multiple sources, hence, having non-established standards is expected to significantly hinder the practical establishment of the framework.
- **Citation standards for software and training contributions.** Software tools and training activities are fundamental in modern science and are often being cited in research publications (especially software). A standardized citation framework for these activities would not only ensure proper attribution but also provide insights about their usage and impact in the scientific community. It can also incentivise their development and maintenance, fostering a culture of collaboration. Finally, unified citation practices would enhance the discoverability and reuse of software and training resources, ultimately strengthening the research ecosystem as a whole.
- **Contribution role taxonomies for software- and training-related activities.** The existence of taxonomies for contribution roles in research software development and training activities is essential for ensuring that all contributors receive appropriate recognition for their efforts. These activities often involve diverse roles, ranging from coding, testing, and documentation to designing training curricula, delivering workshops, and supporting community engagement. Without a clear and standardized taxonomy, the varied contributions risk being homogenized or overlooked, which can

³⁹ Barcelona DORI: <https://barcelona-declaration.org/>

lead to inequities in credit allocation and discourage participation in these vital activities.

Regarding the platforms, the following categories are of particular importance:

- **Research Publishing Platforms.** These platforms are designed to collect, maintain, and publish research assets submitted by researchers, including research software code and training materials, as well as information related to the respective research activities (e.g., software development and documentation, training events). They may also assign persistent identifiers (PIDs) to these assets and gather basic metadata related to them. Indicative examples of such platforms include Research Asset Repositories (e.g., source code repositories like GitHub, preprint repositories like Zenodo⁴⁰ and ArXiv⁴¹), Research Journals & Publishers, and Research Activity Registries (e.g., ELIXIR TeSS⁴² And OpenPlato⁴³ for training events).
- **Researcher PID Providers:** These platforms provide researchers with persistent identifiers (PIDs), which can be used during the submission of research assets to ensure unique identification. Publishing platforms incorporate researcher PIDs in the assets' metadata, enabling aggregators and recognition platforms to appropriately recognize a researcher's activities and contributions. ORCID⁴⁴ is a well-known example of a researcher PID providing platform.
- **Research Metadata Enrichment Platforms.** These platforms enrich the basic research asset metadata provided by the Research Publishing Platforms with missing annotations. The types of annotations vary according to the availability of metadata registered in the publishing platforms to be enriched. The enrichments could be automatically generated or curated by humans. Indicative examples include research performance indicators, contribution roles (e.g., CRediT-based), topics, and more.
- **Research Metadata Aggregators.** These platforms collect, merge, de-duplicate, clean, and homogenize research-related metadata from various sources, providing end users with easy access to the aggregated information. Indicative examples of such platforms are Crossref⁴⁵, which collects scholarly metadata from various publishers, and the OpenAIRE Graph⁴⁶ that collects metadata from thousands of publication repositories and other open sources of scholarly information. In many cases, Research Metadata Aggregators are accessible for querying and processing in the form of Knowledge Graphs, often referred to as Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs).
- **Researcher Contribution Trackers.** These platforms aim to track the connections between researchers and research contributions or activities. As it is evident, this type of platform is crucial in enabling proper crediting for researchers. Indicative examples of such platforms are ORCID, which collects various types of contributions by

⁴⁰ Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/>

⁴¹ ArXiv: <http://arxiv.org/>

⁴² ELIXIR TeSS: <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

⁴³ OpenPlato: <https://openplato.eu/>

⁴⁴ ORCID: <http://orcid.org/>

⁴⁵ Crossref: <https://www.crossref.org/>

⁴⁶ OpenAIRE Graph: <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

researchers (e.g., publications, datasets), and APICURON⁴⁷, which tracks research database curation contributions by researchers.

- **Research Achievement Gamification Platforms.** These platforms collect research-related information from Research Metadata Aggregators and Researcher Contribution Trackers to provide Gamification features, such as badges and leaderboards, to incentivise research work. APICURON is a platform that offers such features to researchers for database curation activities.
- **Academic Profile Platforms.** These platforms collect information from Research Metadata Aggregators and Researcher Contribution Trackers to create and make publicly available academic profiles that facilitate recognition and enable sharing and comprehension of research contributions. These platforms summarise a researcher's contributions often offering also relevant analytics and visualizations. ORCID offers academic Profile functionality. Another indicative example that supports various types of profile templates is BIP! Scholar⁴⁸.

This platform classification draws heavily from the categories identified in the report accompanying Milestone MS3.1 of the ELIXIR-STEERS project (Bouhraoua, A. et al. 2024). These categories were later refined to clarify distinctions between them. Additionally, the modifications incorporated insights from discussions within CoARA's OI4RRA working group⁴⁹, which focused on developing a conceptual architecture for implementing a responsible research assessment framework built on open infrastructures.

5.3 Gaps, Challenges, and Opportunities

In this section, we conduct a preliminary gap analysis to assess the current state of Credit, Recognition, and Rewards in research work in relevance to research software and training activities. We examine the challenges and opportunities in bridging the identified gaps, aiming to lay the groundwork for a robust and inclusive credit, recognition, and rewards framework.

Focusing first on the necessary standards for research software-related contributions, there are several relevant efforts that need to be reported. In recent years, various initiatives have aimed to establish metadata standards for key types of research outputs. Notably, the RDA's Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework⁵⁰ (SKG-IF) Working Group has been working to develop a common language for all Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), ensuring consistency in the terminology used when exposing fundamental scholarly metadata. This framework explicitly includes software as a distinct category of research products. Beyond that, other widely established standards, such as CodeMeta, address similar needs. Consequently, we could conclude that there is significant process in determining common metadata standards for software, though further alignment may still be necessary to ensure greater consistency and interoperability.

⁴⁷ APICURON: <https://apicuron.org/>

⁴⁸ BIP! Scholar: <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/scholar>

⁴⁹ OI4RRA WG: <https://coara.eu/working-groups/working-groups/wg-towards-open-infrastructures-for-responsible-research-assessment-oi4rra/>

⁵⁰ SKG-IF: <https://skg-if.github.io/>

Efforts to standardize software citation practices have also gained momentum in recent years, recognizing the critical role of software in research. Indicatively, the FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group⁵¹ published in 2016 a set of principles emphasizing the importance of software citation (Smith AM et al. 2016). These principles advocate for proper credit and attribution, unique identification, persistence, accessibility, and specificity in software citations. Building on these principles, in 2019, a report titled “Software Citation Implementation Challenges” (Katz D. S. et al. 2019) examined issues impacting scholarly attribution of research software, provided updated implementation guidance, and identified where best practices and solutions were still needed. Further developments came in 2021 with comprehensive software citation guidelines for academic journals and conference proceedings (Katz D. S. et al. 2021). In 2022, the HEP Software Foundation and the Institute for Research and Innovation for Software in High-Energy Physics organized a workshop on the topic of Software Citation and Recognition in HEP and the key findings and recommendations were presented at the 26th International Conference on Computing in High Energy and Nuclear Physics and in a relevant report (Feickert, M. et al. 2023).

Contributions to research software can vary widely, involving diverse roles such as software architect, coder, debugger, tester, and team manager. This diversity complicates the assignment of credit and recognition to individuals involved in software development. Several initiatives are attempting to provide controlled vocabularies for the related activities including the generic CRO, the more focused INRIA’s Taxonomy for Software Contributions and The Software Credit Taxonomy (see also Section 5.1). However, increased alignment seems to be needed, similarly to other standards.

Regarding training activities, various standards have been developed to address recognition and credit attribution in educational contexts. The Dublin Core⁵² standard offers a simplified set of metadata elements applicable to a wide range of resources, including educational content. Its elements, like creator, subject, and date, support basic resource description and enhance interoperability. Moreover, the IEEE LOM standard provides a comprehensive framework for describing learning resources. It includes elements such as title, description, keywords, and technical requirements, facilitating consistent cataloguing and retrieval of educational materials. In addition, ISO/IEC 19788⁵³ (Metadata for Learning Resources - MLR) multi-part standard aims to specify data elements for the description of learning resources, promoting consistency and interoperability in educational metadata. It builds upon existing standards like LOM and Dublin Core, providing a structured approach to metadata application. Finally, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) has developed a Minimal Metadata Set for Learning Resources (Hoebelheinrich, N. J. et al. 2022) to aid in the harmonized discovery of learning resources. This set is subject-agnostic and includes specific elements relevant to training, facilitating the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles in educational contexts.

Regarding citing training activities and materials, while standardized practices are not as well-established as those for software, there are initiatives aimed at improving their discoverability and proper acknowledgement. A notable example is the article “Ten Simple Rules for Making Training Materials FAIR” (Garcia L et al 2020) which provides guidelines to enhance the

⁵¹ FORCE11 Software Citation WG: <https://force11.org/group/software-citation-working-group>

⁵² <https://www.dublincore.org/>

⁵³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/62845.html>

Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Re-usability (FAIR) of training resources. These rules emphasize the importance of sharing materials online, providing proper descriptions, and using standardized metadata to facilitate proper citation and reuse. Additionally, general citation standards like ISO 690⁵⁴ offer guidelines for referencing various types of information resources, which can be applied to training materials. This standard specifies the elements that should be included in bibliographic references and the order in which they should appear, providing a framework that can be adapted for citing training activities and materials. By following these guidelines and utilizing existing citation standards, creators and users of training materials can promote consistent acknowledgement and enhance the integration of these resources into scholarly work. Finally, generic taxonomies for contribution roles (such as CRO - see also Section 5.1) offer a controlled vocabulary for training activities. However, more focused taxonomies may be needed.

Shifting the focus to the necessary platforms, there is already strong representation across most identified categories, with existing platforms well-equipped to support credit and recognition mechanisms that account for research software and training activities. First of all, this is the case for Research Publishing Platforms. Code repositories, like GitHub, and other software repositories or registries, like the WorkflowHub⁵⁵ (for scientific workflows), bio.tools⁵⁶ (for life science software tools), and Docker Hub⁵⁷ (for containers), are well-established and their use is a standard practice for researchers involved in research software projects. At the same time, general-purpose research asset repositories, like Zenodo, support the creation of software entries and training material minting persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) for them. Various journals and conferences support publishing specialized articles describing research software projects. Finally, there is a variety of research activity registries that specifically track training activities, such as ELIXIR TeSS and OpenPlato.

Moreover, ORCID is a community standard Researcher PID provider. ORCID identifiers are widely used by researchers from various domains and are supported by scientific publishers and research funding organisations to enable the unique identification of individuals. While other researcher identifiers exist, such as ResearcherID (by Web of Science) and profile codes from platforms like Google Scholar, ORCID IDs remain the most widely adopted persistent identifiers in research, though not all researchers have one.

Regarding the research metadata enrichment, there is a variety of platforms offering diverse types of enrichments. Indicatively, the SciNoBo Fields of Science classification platform⁵⁸ automatically assigns fields and topics to research publications, while the BIP! Ranker⁵⁹ (Kanelos I. et al, 2024) calculates citation-based impact indicators for research products. The Tools Observatory of the OpenEBench platform provides various indicators for research software availability and performance. These platforms typically integrate their enrichments into Research Metadata Aggregators. For instance, both SciNoBo and BIP! Ranker feed into the OpenAIRE Graph. Apart from those focusing exclusively on software, usually the focus of enrichment platforms is on publications and there is space for improvement in supporting

⁵⁴ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:690:ed-4:v1:en>

⁵⁵ WorkflowHub: <https://workflowhub.eu/>

⁵⁶ Bio.tools: <https://bio.tools/>

⁵⁷ Docker Hub: <https://hub.docker.com/>

⁵⁸ SciNoBo FoS: <https://github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-fos-classification>

⁵⁹ BIP! Ranker: <https://github.com/athenarc/Bip-Ranker>

similar enrichments for research software and training activities. Indicatively, although BIP! Ranker supports calculating citation-based impact indicators for research software projects, those indicators are based on direct citations of publications to software DOIs. However, this is expected to collect only a fraction of the software project's impact since it is very common for researchers to cite the corresponding software article or simply mention the software repository inside the manuscript (e.g., in a footnote). As a result, an extension of the platform is needed to support more comprehensive indicators for research software projects. Similar cases can be found for other enrichment platforms in the case of software- and training-related activities or material. Since BIP! Ranker is part of the ecosystem supporting the BIP! Scholar academic profile platform, in the context of EVERSE it is expected to be extended towards enhanced support for research software and training activities.

In recent years, various organizations have provided open Research Metadata Aggregators. This trend aligns with Open Science initiatives that advocate for platforms for sharing open research information, like the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information⁶⁰. Among the most widely known open aggregators are OpenAlex and the OpenAIRE Graph. OpenAlex focuses on publications and basic research-related entities, such as researchers, institutions, and grants. The OpenAIRE Graph has a broader focus also covering datasets, software and other types of research products (including training material). The OpenAIRE Graph has a great potential in assisting credit and recognition for research software and training activities, and the participation in EVERSE offers good opportunities for improvements. For instance, the coverage of training activities is currently limited because aggregators lack established connections with important research activity registries like ELIXIR TeSS. Improved interoperability in such platforms would help address this gap.

Regarding Researcher Contribution Trackers, ORCID is the most widely used and, it supports tracking for each researcher a wide variety of research works (publications, books, datasets, software, etc.), peer reviewing activity, research funding, and other types of contributions. Since ORCID is a general-purpose tracker, the information captured for some types of contributions is rather basic and this creates the necessity of other, more specialised tracking platforms to address the need of keeping more detailed information for them. An indicative example is APICURON that focuses on tracking database curation activities in detail supporting to push generalised entries for the same contributions to ORCID. In the context of the EVERSE project, APICURON is expected to be extended so that it can also cover similar type of information for research software and training activities.

APICURON is also an indicative platform offering Research Achievement Gamification functionalities. More specifically, it offers leaderboard and badging functionalities encouraging greater engagement in time-consuming and routine tasks such as database record curation. In the context of EVERSE, APICURON aims to support similar functionalities for activities related to research software and training. In general, there is an increasing need for this type of platform focusing on this type of activity.

Finally, when it comes to Academic Profile Platforms, a wide range of services is already available. ORCID is a key example, though its profiles primarily serve as structured lists of contributions with basic metadata about researchers. Other platforms, such as Google

⁶⁰ Barcelona DORI: <https://barcelona-declaration.org/>

Scholar⁶¹, provide profile functionalities but are largely centred on publications, as these are the most readily available metadata. BIP! Scholar is a platform that takes a broader approach by supporting multiple profile templates tailored to diverse researcher needs. These templates may incorporate various researcher-level indicators or support modern formats, such as narrative CVs, to provide a more comprehensive representation of academic contributions. As part of the EVERSE project, BIP! Scholar is set to be expanded to better accommodate academic profile templates that emphasize research software and training activities, ensuring a more holistic approach to researcher recognition. The need to better incorporate profile elements that better track activities related to research software and training are crucial for the implementation of an inclusive credit and recognition framework.

⁶¹ Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/>

6 Conclusion

In the landscape of contemporary research, the roles and responsibilities of researchers have evolved significantly, encompassing diverse activities that extend beyond traditional scholarly outputs. This evolution prompts a critical examination of how we assess and recognize these multifaceted contributions within the academic and scientific communities. The pursuit of a comprehensive framework for research assessment and recognition is imperative to ensure equitable acknowledgement of all valuable research endeavours, including dataset creation, software development, training initiatives, and educational contributions. Such a framework not only supports researchers in their career progression but also cultivates a culture that values and incentivises excellence across all dimensions of research practice.

This report explores the foundational initiatives and principles shaping contemporary discourse on research assessment and recognition. Drawing upon influential initiatives, such as the Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) and the Coalition for Reforming Research Assessment (CoARA), it seeks to distil key insights and recommendations for advancing fair, transparent, and inclusive evaluation practices. By synthesising the diverse perspectives and innovative approaches outlined in these initiatives and by scoping the existing standards and platforms that can contribute to the implementation of the respective practices, this report aims to contribute to the development of a robust and inclusive framework tailored to recognize and reward research activities, particularly in the domains of Research Software Engineering and training offering also key insights about the opportunities and challenges related to its implementation.

The landscape analysis reveals a diverse array of good practices, standards, and platforms that can support the implementation of a more inclusive research assessment framework. However, there remain key gaps, including the need for specific functionalities, improved interoperability, and enhanced standardization across existing platforms. Addressing these challenges will be crucial in optimizing their effectiveness and ensuring seamless implementation. EVERSE will take into consideration these results to better design the relevant tasks of the project plan.

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Annex

Appendix A: Table of relevant resources

The list of resources collected to create the current report can be found in the following table:

Resource	Relevant URL	Type
The Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)	https://sfedora.org/	Initiative
Leiden Manifesto	http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/	Initiative
The Hong Kong Principles for Assessing Researchers	https://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article?id=10.1371/journal.pbio.3000737	Initiative
The Hidden REF	https://hidden-ref.org/about/	Initiative
HELIOS Open	https://www.heliosopen.org/	Initiative
Coalition for Reforming Research Assessment (CoARA)	https://coara.eu/	Initiative
Common European Research Information Format (CERIF)	https://eurocris.org/eurocris_archive/cerifsupport.org/cerif-in-brief/index.html	Standard
Citation File Format (CFF)	https://citation-file-format.github.io/	Standard
CodeMeta	https://codemeta.github.io/	Standard
CRedit	https://credit.niso.org	Standard
CODEOWNERS	https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/managing-your-repositorys-settings-and-features/customizing-your-repository/about-code-owners	Standard
Contributor Role Ontology (CRO)	https://github.com/data2health/contributor-role-ontology	Standard
DataCite's Contributor Types	https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.5/appendices/appendix-1/contributorType/	Standard
Dublic Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI)	https://www.dublincore.org/	Standard
GraspOS API specification	https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/api-spec	Standard
INRIA's Taxonomy for Research Contributions	https://hal.science/hal-02135891	Standard
OpenAIRE Guidelines	https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/	Standard
Open Badges	https://openbadges.org/	Standard
OpenSSF Badges	https://www.bestpractices.dev/en	Standard
Scholarly Contributions and Roles Ontology (SCoRo)	https://sparontologies.github.io/scoro/current/scoro.html	Standard
Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF)	https://skg-if.github.io/	Standard
The Software Credit Taxonomy	https://dagstuhleas.github.io/SoftwareCreditRoles/doc/index-en.html	Standard
ArXiv (Research asset repository)	https://arxiv.org/	Platform
APICURON	https://apicuron.org/	Platform
BadgEd (Open Digital Badges)	https://information-services.ed.ac.uk/learning-technology/more/badged-open-digital-badges	Platform
BIP! Scholar	https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/scholar	Platform
DORA Reformscape	https://sfedora.org/reformscape/discover-reformscape/	Platform
DORA Resource Library	https://sfedora.org/resource-library/	Platform
ELIXIR's Training e-Support System (TeSS)	https://tess.elixir-europe.org/	Platform
FAIR Software Checklist	https://fairsoftwarechecklist.net/v0.2/	Platform
GitHub (Research asset repository)	https://github.com/	Platform
GitLab (Research asset repository)	https://about.gitlab.com/	Platform
GraspOS Infrastructure	https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/	Platform
HAL (Research asset repository)	https://hal.science/	Platform
OERSI (Open Educational Resource Search Index)	https://oersi.org/resources/	Platform
OpenAIRE Graph	https://graph.openaire.eu/	Platform
OpenAlex	https://openalex.org/	Platform
OpenEBench Tools Observatory	https://openebench.bsc.es/observatory/	Platform
OpenPlato	https://openplato.eu/	Platform
ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)	https://orcid.org/	Platform
Research Software Encyclopaedia (RSE)	https://github.com/rseng/rse	Platform
Software Citation Station	https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.04405	Platform
WorkflowHub	https://workflowhub.eu/	Platform
Zenodo (Research asset repository)	https://zenodo.org/	Platform

Appendix B: List of Abbreviations

AI: Artificial Intelligence
ARRA: Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment
CERIF: Common European Research Information Format
CFF: Citation File Format
CoARA: Coalition for Reforming Research Assessment
DMP: Data Management Plan
DORA: Declaration on Research Assessment
EC: European Commission
EOSC: European Open Science Cloud
EU: European Union
FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GRC: Global Research Council
HKPs: Hong Kong Principles
IG: Interest Group
IF: Interoperability Framework
NIH: National Institutes of Health
OER: Open Educational Resource
OS: Open Science
PID: Persistent Identifier
RDA: Research Data Alliance
REF: Research Excellence Framework
REG: Research Evaluation Group
RFO: Research Funding Organisation
RPO: Research Performing Organisation
ReSA: Research Software Alliance
RSE: Research Software Engineer
SKG: Scientific Knowledge Graph
SRIA: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TF: Task Force
WG: Working Group